

Hidden Barriers: Graduate Students in STEM & Possible Obstructions to Researcher Identification

Abstract

There is a general need to increase the number of STEM professionals, but the need to increase the number of individuals who pursue STEM research careers is acute. Because research careers require advanced training, a key aspect to increasing the number of STEM professionals in these areas is their graduate education experiences—specifically their relationship with research communities. Accordingly, this pilot study explores researcher identity development for STEM graduate students, with an emphasis on how important psychosocial factors (i.e., campus climate, belongingness and mentoring) may shape this outcome. The findings suggest minimal relationships between climate, belongingness and the outcome; however, the data point towards a negative association between mentoring and researcher identification. Implications for practice and future research are discussed.

There have been longstanding conversations about the need to increase the number of students pursuing STEM degrees and careers. While the overarching emphasis on increasing the number of STEM professionals remains, there is an acute need to increase the number of individuals who pursue STEM research careers, specifically, to ensure future advancements in research and development in industry and government. Because research careers often require advanced training in a STEM area, a key aspect to increasing the number of STEM professionals in research careers will be their experiences during their graduate education. Specifically, it is important to better understand how students' identity as researchers develop during this critical stage of their educational and professional development. To better understand this overarching process, this pilot study explores the research identity development process for graduate students, with an emphasis on now important social and psychological (i.e., psychosocial) factors may shape this outcome. At the social and psychological levels, this study examines how students' perceptions of the campus climate and their sense of belonging (SOB) in that environment may influence their research identification. These factors are important given research which indicates how students' campus experiences and perceptions of the environment can positively impact their academic and social development, as well as other important outcomes [1], [2], [3]. Also at the social level, this analysis focuses on mentoring and how such experiences may shape student's researcher identity development over and beyond their campus climate perceptions and aspects of their belonging. The following primary research questions guide these analyses:

1) How do graduate students' perceptions of campus climate and SOB relate to their researcher identity? and

2) Does the relationship between student's perception of campus climate, SOB and research identity differ after accounting for student's mentoring experiences?

These findings will provide useful insights to help institutions to better understand how to develop a stronger connection to research opportunities and careers for graduate students in STEM.

Literature Review

Identity

Aspects of students' identity are often discussed in both academic and non-academic spaces and identity is frequently positioned as a key facet for: improving outcomes in STEM fields, and understanding students' overall academic and professional trajectories. Identity theory has been a prominent area of study for several decades within social psychology and other disciplines [4]. Multiple approaches for theorizing the concept of identity have emerged since its inception. However, one commonality across these approaches relates to the different factors that can shape a persons' identity—the role an individual inhabits, group membership, and personal characteristics that make an individual unique [4]. Role identity represents “a set of internalized meanings associated with a role” [4] or social position. Group identity is determined by involvement with others in a particular group, adopting and attempting to fulfill the expected behaviors for a given group, as well as participation in activities for a specific group [4]. Personal identity represents aspects of an individual that defines a person in distinct ways and go beyond a given role or group affiliation (e.g., seeing oneself as having high morals, integrity or assertiveness) [4]. Each of these elements of identity can overlap and people can occupy multiple identities simultaneously [4], [5]. Given the various ways of conceptualizing this construct, in this study, identity is broadly defined as a type of self-perception which is shaped by individual and social factors and provides insights about how a person thinks about himself, herself or themselves. Moreover, this study examines researcher identity specifically to examine how STEM graduate students view themselves in relation to conducting research given the growing workforce need in this area.

Campus climate

Campus climate is described in many ways [6] but can be broadly defined as “students' perceptions of their experiences both in and out of the classroom” [7]. In this study, department climate represents similar perceptions, specifically as they relate to experiences within students' department of study. Various scholars have studied these aspects of institutional environments and how they shape students' experiences [7], [8], [9], [10]. However, understudied is the manner in which campus climate may impact how graduate students engage the research process—especially how these environments may impact their research identity at institutions that place a large emphasis on research productivity.

Sense of Belonging

Belongingness has often been studied within higher education context, with a focus on its impact on student success. SOB represents “students' perceived social support on campus, a feeling or sensation of connectedness, and the experience of mattering or feeling cared about, accepted, respected, valued by, and important to the campus community or others on campus such as faculty, staff, and peers.” [11]. Overall, the literature suggest that SOB predicts students' intentions to persist in college [12] and that students with higher SOB also have higher emotional and behavior engagement on campus [13]. While there is a robust body of literature concerning belongingness and its positive implications on educational outcomes, the bulk of this literature has examined these issues at the undergraduate level. Furthermore, few studies have examined SOB within particular facets of campus and how it may impact academic development for graduate students.

Mentoring

Mentoring is another important facet of higher education with numerous studies noting its positive impact on student development [14]. Literature suggests the mentoring can manifest in multiple capacities, including peer-to-peer mentoring; faculty-student mentoring; informal mentoring relationship and formal mentoring programs [15]. For graduate students, supportive mentoring relationships have been found to enhance student's socialization, program satisfaction, and writing/research productivity—particularly in STEM [15]. As a compliment to this body of research, this analysis examines the role of mentoring relationship on STEM graduate students' researcher identity.

Conceptual Framework

The Bowman Role Strain and Adaptation Model (BRSAM) provides a useful conceptual lens for this study which explores how psychosocial factors relate to graduate student's researcher identity development [16]. BRSAM is a strength-based framework which underscores the importance of students' strengths and strains on their academic and career outcomes. This model has been used in various STEM education studies [17], [18], [19] including research concerning graduate students [20].

Building upon existing role strain literature, Bowman [16] defines student role strain as the challenges that individuals face in their role as students. As a strength-based model, in addition to strain, BRSAM emphasizes the social and psychological strengths that students can draw from to promote successful outcomes [16]. Key social strengths include a positive institutional environment and positive social interactions or supports—each of which relate to perceptions of campus climate, SOB therein and key aspects of mentoring. Building upon the research previously noted, this study employs the BRSAM to underscore the importance of psychosocial factors on student success, with an emphasis on how these factors may shape the degree to which graduate students develop strong identities as researchers.

Methods

In Fall 2019, survey data was collected from graduate students in a computing department at a large, research-focused institution. A total of 66 students are included in this pilot analysis. Survey questions inquired about students': perception of the campus climate; SOB; mentoring experiences and identification as researchers. Campus climate was measured at the department level given that graduate students' campus experiences are often largely confined within these units. Study participants were also queried about SOB both within their department and the overall university. Moreover, students indicated whether they had a mentor within their departments. Measures for each are included in the study, along with data concerning student's gender and domesticity (i.e., international student or domestic student).

Overall descriptive statistics were examined, along with correlations to examine bivariate relationships between measures. Because the outcome in this study was continuous, ordinary least squares (OLS) was an appropriate analytic technique [21]. Moreover, hierarchical OLS was used to better determine 1) if the amount of variance in the outcome explained increases once students' mentoring experiences are considered in addition to their campus climate perceptions and SOB; and 2) whether the nature of the relationship between climate perceptions, SOB and researcher identity differs after accounting for mentoring experience. The first model in the analyses includes important background characteristics as controls. The second model adds the

measures for campus climate and belongingness. The third and final model includes a measure for mentoring. Each of the measures in these analyses are standardized.

Findings

Background Characteristic

No differences emerged between females and male with regards to graduate students' researcher identity. Although the data initially suggested that domestic graduate students had a lower researcher identity when compared to international graduate students (model 1), this difference was no longer statistically significant after accounting for student's perception of campus climate and SOB (model 2).

Climate and Belonging

In model 2, graduate students' SOB within the university was negatively related to graduate students' researcher identity. This negative relationship remained after accounting for students mentoring experiences, although the relationship was then marginally significant (model 2). Graduate students' SOB in their department was positively and marginally related to their researcher identity (model 2); however, this relationship was no longer statistically significant after accounting for their mentoring experience (model 3).

Mentoring

All else being equal, graduate students who indicated having a mentor within their departments were less researcher identified than their peers who did not have a department mentor (model 3).

Discussion and Implications

The findings provide useful insight concerning how various campus experiences may help to shape the degree to which graduate students begin to identify as researchers during their academic trajectories. Surprisingly, graduate students' perceptions of campus climate was not related to their researcher identity development; and their SOB within the university appears to be minimally related to this outcome. Although marginal, the negative relationship between university SOB and researcher identity is compelling given that the graduate students in this study attended an institution highly regarded for its research productivity. Nonetheless, these preliminary results suggest that researcher identity may develop independent from feeling a part of the university community or the departmental community. Perhaps a more tailored examination of belongingness within research communities would be more insightful given the nature of the outcome.

One of the most compelling findings from this study relates to the negative association between mentoring and researcher identity. The findings suggest that graduate students who have mentors in their departments are less researcher identified than those without such mentors. The nature of this relationship is counter intuitive given existing literature which highlights the positive impact of mentoring on student's education and career development [14, [15]. Accordingly, this finding suggests a need for further investigation about the nature of these mentoring relationships. Questions to consider include: what kind of mentoring relationships do students have in their departments? Who is serving as mentors? How are these mentoring relationships arranged? Do they develop organically or is there obligatory pairing via existing programs on campus? What is the nature of the interaction between mentors and mentees? Are

mentoring relationship specifically related to research or more generic in nature? While additional quantitative data may provide further insight, qualitative data may also be a useful supplement to better understand critical aspects of these mentoring relationships. Nonetheless, these preliminary findings may suggest a need for institutions to take a closer look at mentoring experiences on campus and the degree to which they may discourage graduate students feeling connected to research communities in salient ways. This is especially important if these mentoring relationships are primarily with faculty within departments.

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Table 1.

Correlation Matrix							
	Researcher Identity	Domestic	Female	Department Campus Climate	Sense of Belonging in University	Sense of Belonging in Department	Mentor in Department
Researcher Identity	.	-.326**	-0.101	-0.091	-.330*	-0.037	-.534**
Domestic		.	0.110	0.219	.416**	0.031	.591**
Female			.	-0.242	0.090	-0.028	0.036
Department Campus Climate				.	.439**	.431**	-0.041
Sense of Belonging in University					.	.730**	0.247
Sense of Belonging in Department						.	-0.103
Mentor in Department							.

~ p<.10; * p<.05; ** p<.01; *** p<.001

Table 2.

Hierarchical Regression Analysis Assessing the Influence of Campus Climate, Belongingness and Mentoring on Graduate Student Researcher Identity (n=66)

Independent Variables	Model 1: Background Characteristics	Model 2: Climate & Belonging	Model 3: Mentoring Experience
<u>Background</u>			
Domestic	-0.79 *	-0.26	0.39
Female	-0.14	-0.06	-0.17
<u>Climate & Belonging</u>			
Department Campus Climate (a)		0.01	-0.09
Sense of Belonging in University (a)		-0.56 *	-0.39 ~
Sense of Belonging in Department (a)		0.37 ~	0.23
<u>Mentoring Experience</u>			
Mentor in Department			-0.51 **
Constant	0.207	0.072	-0.023
R ²	0.11 *	0.21 *	0.36 *
Change in R ²		0.1	0.15 **

~ p<.10; * p<.05; ** p<.01; *** p<.001

(a) Variables are z-scores (M=0; SD=1); Unstandardized coefficients reported